

Metadata

Title*

Exploring roles, career pathways and team science in biomedical data science: a case study approach

Description*

Data and data science are transforming the world, and expertise in this area is in increasingly high demand. In biomedical research, there is an urgent need for a shared framework that defines data science careers, enabling skills mobility and the recognition of biomedical data science roles and team-based approaches across different organisational contexts.

To better understand roles, career pathways, and team science approaches within the biomedical data science community, and how these factors can improve access and career development, we are conducting a case study analysis. This study will document how diverse data science roles and collaborative team structures have been implemented across different types and scales of organisations engaged in biomedical data science research.

In this qualitative study, we aim to gather a wide range of lived experiences to surface key challenges, opportunities, incentives, and gaps in current practice. Our case study analysis will focus on three levels:

- Organisational level: Examining how data science roles and teams are established and supported, with a focus on resourcing and advocacy for new roles.
- Team level: Exploring how collaborative team science has been successfully approached and managed within teams.
- Individual level: Documenting career pathway examples to showcase diverse role models who have successfully navigated careers in biomedical data science.

Our intended contribution is to provide a focused evaluation and a set of recommendations on innovative approaches and ways of working that can support capacity building and improve quality and standards in biomedical data science in the UK.

Contributors*

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Subject*

Our system uses the [bepress taxonomy](#). Please select as many subjects as you please. Note, the more detailed and inclusive you are in your response makes it easier for others to find your work.

Life Sciences

Medicine and Health Sciences

Bioinformatics

Translational Medical Research

Study Information

Research Aims*

Please specify the overall purposes, objectives or aims of the research.

If relevant, please reflect on whether your aim is different across different domains (e.g. knowledge generation, policy development, community resourcing). If so, specify your aim for each domain that is relevant for your study.

Overall purpose: To provide a focused evaluation and practical recommendations on

successful and innovative approaches that support capacity building and enhance quality and standards in interdisciplinary biomedical data science.

Aim: To document a broad range of interdisciplinary biomedical data science to better understand skills, roles, career pathways and team science approaches.

Objectives: To describe a diverse range of skills, roles, career pathways and team science approaches within the biomedical data science community.

- To understand what successful and innovative interdisciplinary biomedical data science is.
- To understand successful career pathways within biomedical data science.
- To understand the roles needed within biomedical data science teams.

If helpful, please select the type of aim (non-exhaustive list):

- Exploring
- Describing
- Theory evaluating
- Comparing
- Understanding

Research question(s)*

Please specify your research question or questions as they are guiding your research now. If relevant, you may also specify here any hypotheses to be assessed. The research questions may break down your aim into smaller, distinct inquiries.

If relevant, you may distinguish between primary and secondary research questions or hypotheses.

Example: If it is your aim to explore the attitudes of caregivers towards Alzheimer patients in a local ward, your research questions could specify precisely what you plan to study; for instance, how ward staff tries to treat the patients with dignity or how the relationship between the patient and their family members or loved ones evolved since that patient was admitted to the ward.

RQ: How are different data science roles integrated within biomedical teams, and how do team science approaches enable effective collaboration?

SUB-RQ1: How are data science roles defined and structured across different biomedical data science organisations?

SUB-RQ2: What specific data science roles are present in biomedical data science teams, and how are these roles integrated into the team?

SUB-RQ3: How do individuals construct career pathways in biomedical data science?

Anticipated Duration *

Please indicate the estimated project start date (mm/yyyy) and estimated project end date (mm/yyyy).

1st February 2025 to 31st January 2027

Design Plan

Study design *

Please provide a brief, overarching characterisation of the study design.

Your response might consist of a succinct label (e.g., “case study” or “ethnography”) and/or a brief elaboration of that label’s meaning.

A study may involve a combination of different designs, including a mix of quantitative and qualitative methods.

Case study (qualitative)

Sampling and case selection strategy *

Please describe your sampling or recruitment strategy (examples include, but are not limited to: purposive, snowball, theoretical, and maximum variation sampling) and/or your case selection strategy (examples include, but are not limited to: typical case, most similar case, most different case, diverse case, and deviant case).

Please provide a short rationale for why you selected this type of strategy.

Sampling strategy

To achieve our research aim – to document a broad range of skills, roles, career pathways, and team science approaches in biomedical data science – we are employing a case study approach at three levels of analysis:

- Organisational level: how roles and teams are established and implemented, to better understand resourcing and advocacy for new roles.
- Team level: how collaborative team science is successfully approached and managed within teams.
- Individual level: examples of career pathways, highlighting a diverse set of role models who have successfully navigated this space.

We are aiming for a maximum variation sampling method, and we will ensure the diversity of the sample by assessing saturation at different sampling stages. We will begin with purposive sampling to select participants with relevant experiences for the study. These participants will be drawn from known biomedical data science organisations, identified through our prior knowledge of the

landscape and existing partnerships. Initial sampling will take place at The Alan Turing Institute and EMBL-EBI. We will then move on to engage a wider group of existing partners. Saturation will be assessed, and subsequent sampling will be guided by our stakeholder mapping to ensure sufficient diversity in the study. At this stage, we will approach organisations and individuals directly, while also issuing an open call to the wider biomedical data science community and advertising at various workshops and events to attract specific case studies.

Case selection

We aim to collect diverse and influential cases, those that demonstrate the breadth of work and approaches present in interdisciplinary biomedical data science, including innovative ways of working. We will document both positive and challenging experiences to enable a more comprehensive analysis. Below is an overview of our inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Case	Included	Excluded
Organisation		
Type of organisation	Biomedical and Data Science	Data Science only; Biomedical only
Geographical location	UK-based (<i>including international organisations that have an active presence in the UK, with an office/division in the country</i>)	Non UK-based
Sector	All sectors included	None
Team		
Team structure	Interdisciplinary/Multidisciplinary /Transdisciplinary	N/A
	Discipline-based	N/A
Project	Team research	Individual research
Team size	5+	0-5
Individual		
Team structure	Embedded	N/A
	Separate	N/A
Project	Team research	Individual research
Career stage	Early career research professionals onwards	Undergraduates

We consciously decided to omit job roles as a selection criterion at the individual level, as job roles in interdisciplinary biomedical data science are often arbitrarily assigned, limited in definition, and frequently self-defined. Therefore, all individuals actively involved in biomedical data science work, regardless of their official job title, are considered potential participants in our study, provided that all other criteria are met.

Data Collection

Data source(s) and data type(s) *

Please describe the type(s) of data you will be using. In describing the data, distinguish between data that existed prior to your study (e.g. archival documents, newspaper articles, [social] media, secondary literature, or data collected for a different purpose than the current study) and original data (i.e. data that will be collected/generated for the current study).

The data collection in our study includes both primary and secondary sources.

Secondary data:

- Scientific literature and white papers: This includes both primary and secondary literature on interdisciplinary biomedical data science and team science approaches.
- Internal documents: Project reports from the organisations leading on this research (The Alan Turing Institute and EMBL-EBI), highlighting findings and insights from previous studies and projects related to interdisciplinarity and diverse professional roles in data science.
- Documentation from the organisations included as case studies, when relevant and accessible.

Primary data:

- Original data collected from professionals working in biomedical data science who meet our selection criteria.

Data collection methods *

Please describe your method of data collection or data generation. Examples of methods include (but are not restricted to) interviews, focus groups, enabling techniques, self-reports, field notes, diaries, (participative) observation, archival research, or mixed methods. Please provide a brief rationale for why you plan to use this particular data collection/generation method in your study.

1) Narrative literature review

As team science approaches in biomedical data science are still an under-researched evolving

topic, we start our data collection with a narrative literature review. Rooted in the humanities and social sciences tradition, a narrative literature review allows researchers to explore what is known about a broad topic through a subjective examination of the scholarship. It analyses the current state of the field, offers insights for advancing it, and considers existing evidence from different or unconventional perspectives (Sukhera, 2022). A narrative review can include a wide variety of studies and provide an overall summary, enabling us to create a suitable contextual background for our investigation.

Our literature review is guided by our research questions, and a set of flexible inclusion criteria and keywords.

- **Search criteria:** Scientific literature and white papers published within the last 5–10 years. This timeframe was chosen because interdisciplinary data science and team science approaches are emerging and still evolving areas of research. Older literature may not reflect recent shifts and developments in the field.
- **Keywords:** biomedical-data-science, team-science, interdisciplinary-science, health-data-science, team-science-health, team-science-biomedical, biomedical-research-data, health-research-data, multidisciplinarity, transdisciplinarity, convergence-research.

2) Semi-structured interviews

Data for this longitudinal, inductive study will be collected at multiple points between September 2025 and December 2026 through qualitative interviews.

Interviews, defined as ‘intensive individual conversations with a small number of respondents to explore their perspectives on a particular idea, program, or situation’ (Boyce & Neale, 2006), are especially well-suited to examining new or poorly understood phenomena. They provide detailed insights into the processes underlying observed patterns and offer access to rich, subjective data that captures participants’ experiences, perspectives, and emotions.

This study will draw on a series of semi-structured interviews, one of the most commonly used techniques in qualitative research (DiCicco-Bloom & Crabtree, 2006). In this format, all interviewees are asked a core set of questions, with flexibility to explore emerging themes or seek clarification as needed. Semi-structured interviews are valued for their balance between consistency and adaptability across diverse research contexts.

We are developing **three interview protocols**, tailored to our research focus at the organisational, team, and individual levels. Each protocol will first be piloted internally to ensure questions are clearly worded and non-leading.

Across all protocols, we have identified **5–7 core questions**, which will be supplemented by context-specific follow-ups. The questions are open-ended, encouraging participants to reflect and elaborate based on their personal experiences and insights. While all interviews will follow the same foundational structure, we expect participants to shape the direction of the conversation. As recurring themes emerge, the protocol may be refined slightly, resulting in interviews that vary in focus and flow.

Interviews are expected to last between 45 and 60 minutes and will be conducted either in person

or online via Microsoft Teams or Zoom. All interviews will be audio-recorded and transcribed verbatim using an AI-powered transcription service.

To favour the inclusion of diverse participants, we are also planning to offer the option of asynchronous email interviews when traditional online or face-to-face interviews are not possible. In this format, interviewees can receive questions by email and reply at their convenience, offering greater flexibility to those with limited availability (e.g., individuals in senior positions). We recognise the potential drawbacks, such as data quality concerns, the need for enhanced clarity and precision in the questions, and the possible loss of follow-up questions that naturally emerge in traditional semi-structured interviews. However, we also believe that asynchronous email interviews can offer distinct benefits, particularly in terms of time efficiency, flexibility, and accessibility.

Participants will always be required to sign a consent form covering both the recording and the use of their data in this research.

Data collection tools, instruments or plans *

Please describe or upload the tools, instruments or plans you will use in collecting or generating your data. Examples could be (but are not limited to): topic guide, interview questionnaire, focus group guide, observation scheme, creative tools (e.g. photos, videos, musical pieces, paintings, etc.), or a description of your archival search plans.

To collect data through qualitative interviews, we will use **three interview protocols** tailored to our research focus at the organisational, team, and individual levels. Each protocol includes 5–7 core questions, supplemented by context-specific follow-ups in line with a semi-structured interview format.

Each participant will receive a **consent form** prior to the interview, outlining the research objectives and main activities, and specifying how the collected data will be used, stored, retained, and shared. All participants must provide written consent to take part in the study.

Following the interview, participants will receive a **post-interview confidentiality form** to complement the pre-interview consent form. This will include four confidentiality options from which participants can choose before any interview data is published or shared beyond the research team. As standard practice, all identifying information will be anonymised unless explicit consent is given for its inclusion in the research and resulting outputs

Stopping criteria *

Please describe the criteria or rationale behind when you will stop data generation or collection. Possible criteria include (but are not restricted to): data saturation*, when inclusion criteria are satisfied, resource constraints (e.g. time/funding), or when the analysis has produced an enriching answer to the research question(s).

Example: We follow Fusch & Ness (2005) and interpret saturation to be reached when there is enough information to replicate the study, the ability to obtain new information has been attained, and further coding is no longer feasible.

Data saturation

As qualitative research does not aim to produce statistically generalisable results, saturation is used as a criterion for discontinuing data collection and/or analysis (Glaser & Strauss, 1967). Saturation is reached when no new insights emerge from the data that contribute to the development or refinement of a category's properties.

We follow Saunders et al. 's (2018b) definition of inductive thematic saturation, which emphasises the identification of new codes or themes, reaching saturation when no further codes or themes can be identified through continued data collection.

Because this approach focuses more explicitly on saturation at the level of analysis, it suggests that saturation cannot be defined a priori at the research design stage. However, focusing on the emergence (or lack thereof) of codes, rather than their theoretical development, still implies that saturation may be achieved at a relatively early stage (opposite to other models, such as theoretical saturation, where saturation occurs at a higher level of theoretical abstraction).

Analysis Plan

Data analysis approach *

Please specify the type and details of your data analysis approach. Examples of approaches include (but are not limited to): narrative analysis, phenomenological analysis, thematic

analysis, content analysis, psychoanalytic analysis, grounded theory, process tracing, comparative analysis, or discourse analysis. If multiple interpretations of your approach exist, please specify the version you will be using. Please provide a rationale for why your selected data analytic approach is appropriate given your study's aim(s).

Example: If you indicated 'phenomenological analysis', you may want to specify the theorist whose approach you are following, e.g. "We use a phenomenological approach as explained by Colaizzi (1978)"; or if you indicated 'content analysis', a specification could be: "We apply inductive content analysis as described in Elo & Kyngäs (2008)".

In this study, we seek to explore the *how* underlying a relatively novel phenomenon within the scientific literature, with particular attention to individuals' experiences, perceptions, and ideas. To support this aim, we are adopting thematic analysis as outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006), due to its flexibility and capacity to generate a nuanced, in-depth account of qualitative data.

Thematic analysis enables researchers to identify patterns of meaning across data sets and examine how these meanings relate to broader social or conceptual contexts. It is among the most widely used methods in qualitative research, offering a structured yet adaptable framework for the iterative development and refinement of emergent themes grounded in participants' narratives.

Thematic analysis involves examining qualitative data by identifying and reporting patterns within the dataset, which are then interpreted for their underlying meaning. These patterns often emerge through attention to the language and keywords used by participants.

The process requires continuous comparison and categorisation of data, allowing abstract or theoretical categories to emerge that reflect latent patterns in participants' perspectives. As the analysis develops, the researcher's experiences and the existing literature in the field guide and inform the categorisation.

Data analysis process *

Please describe what your process of data analysis will look like. Questions to keep in mind could be (but are not limited to):

- * Who will be involved in the data analysis, and in what role?
- * if relevant, indicate any procedures that will be used to turn "raw" data into analyzable form (e.g., a coding scheme)
- * if relevant, indicate any evidentiary criteria that will be used to assess any hypotheses (e.g., what evidence will count as consistent or inconsistent with a given proposition)
- * If relevant, what software or analytic tools will you use and how will you use them?

We adopt an inductive approach, beginning with empirical observations from the data and allowing theories to emerge toward the end of the research process. As such, no hypotheses are formulated in advance. This approach provides us with the flexibility to adjust the direction of the study as insights develop during the course of the analysis.

Authors 1 and 2 will be responsible for analysing the data. We will follow the six-step process of thematic analysis proposed by Naeem et al. (2023), which builds upon Braun and Clarke's (2006) foundational framework, while maintaining the methodological flexibility characteristic of qualitative inquiry.

1. **Transcription, familiarisation with the data, and selection of quotations:** This stage involves transcribing the verbal data, engaging in active and repeated reading of the transcripts, cross-referencing the data, and making preliminary notes on emerging patterns. Early reflections and annotations lay the groundwork for subsequent coding.
2. **Selection of keywords:** A close examination of the interview data allows for the identification of key terms and recurring patterns in participants' experiences, serving as a bridge between raw data and initial codes.
3. **Coding:** Selected excerpts from the data are distilled into concise codes, which are short phrases or terms that encapsulate the underlying meaning. Coding serves as an indexing process, clustering similar ideas and expressions across the dataset.
4. **Theme development:** Codes are grouped into broader, analytically meaningful categories. This step marks a transition from direct observations in the raw data to more abstract patterns, identifying relationships among codes and aligning them with the research questions.
5. **Conceptualisation through interpretation of keywords, codes, and themes:** Emerging themes, codes, and keywords are synthesised to define key concepts and their interconnections. This phase facilitates movement from specific instances to broader interpretations that frame the findings within a conceptual context.
6. **Development of a conceptual model (or report):** The final step involves constructing a comprehensive representation of the data, either in the form of a conceptual model or detailed narrative, to address the research questions and articulate the study's theoretical and/or practical contributions.

Considering the substantial amount of data we aim to collect, we will likely be using QDA computer software during our thematic analysis process, such as NVivo. While the research team is familiar with this tool, we are also exploring other alternatives, and we will make decisions based on what we deem to be the most appropriate tool to analyse our data.

Credibility strategies *

Please specify the strategies, actions or measures you will employ to assure methodological integrity. Examples include (but are not limited to):

- Member checking
- Triangulation with other data sources
- Bringing in different perspectives
- Have different researchers analyse the data
- Consensus building among team members or 'interrater reliability'

- Negative case analysis
- Peer debriefing
- Cross-checks for rivaling explanations
- Bring in an 'auditor'
- Reflexivity
- Verisimilitude
- Emotionality
- Personal Responsibility
- An ethic of caring
- Political praxis
- Multivoiced texts
- Dialogues with subjects
- Other (please explain)

Please provide a short rationale for why you selected particular strategies and how they are appropriate given your study's aim(s) and approach, or specify your credibility strategies if not on the above list. *

As a credibility strategy, we will adopt data **triangulation** and ensure the inclusion of **diverse perspectives** by collecting data from **multiple sources**. Primary data will be gathered through interviews with individuals in a range of roles, seniority levels, and across multiple organisations, rather than relying solely on participants from a single role or institution. Throughout the data analysis process, primary data will be continuously checked against secondary data from scientific literature, as well as white papers and reports published by the partner organisations involved in the research project.

For our research, it will be fundamental to have a very diverse sample that includes a variety of perspectives, experiences, and opinions in order to provide an accurate answer to our research question and make a strong contribution to the field.

It is also important to note that although the researchers are affiliated with the same institution, they come from diverse disciplinary backgrounds and bring a range of professional experiences. This diversity ensures that the data will be viewed through multiple lenses and epistemological frameworks, further enhancing the robustness and credibility of the findings.

Miscellaneous

Reflection on your positionality

Feel free to reflect on your relation to or association with the studied phenomenon and your position in the research setting/field, including your academic/personal standpoints, assumptions and values.

In addition, if there is a potential conflict of interest [whether you have a previous relationship with the studied phenomenon, and if you consider that there are previous positions or

assumptions that may influence the present study] that can arise, you may want to report that here.

Example: If you study the lives of detained immigrants, you might want to talk about your political viewpoints, experience working with detained immigrants, relevant policy work, or perhaps your own experience as a detained immigrant.

This research is part of the Advancing Biomedical Data Science Careers (ABDC) project, funded by the Medical Research Council and jointly delivered by The Alan Turing Institute and EMBL-EBI in the UK (2025–2027).

All authors of this research are white women at mid-to-senior career stages, affiliated with The Alan Turing Institute. We bring a range of disciplinary perspectives and complementary skills, and share a strong commitment to advancing diversity, equity, and inclusion in scientific research. Our work is shaped by institutional practices that promote collaborative approaches and integrated roles within project teams. We have previously worked on adjacent topics and actively advocate for greater interdisciplinarity in science, as well as the adoption of team science approaches to support more effective collaboration.

We acknowledge that both the authorship team and the extended ABDC project team lack broader representation in terms of gender and ethnicity. We recognise this limitation and the potential for blind spots in our research process and outcomes.

To address this, we have established an Advisory Board with near-equal gender representation and ethnically diverse membership. We also engage with the wider UK biomedical data science community through consultation and feedback mechanisms, including workshops and community engagement activities. Pre-registering our study design is part of our broader strategy to increase transparency, invite external feedback, and support research rigour. We aim to make our study as reproducible as possible for qualitative research.

No explicit conflicts of interest have been identified in relation to this research.